

Can We Pay Soon-to-Retire GPs to Work More? Analysis of the Effect of “Goodwill Payments” on GP Behaviour

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ABSTRACT

Aim: Danish general practitioners (GPs) reduce their activity when they are close to retirement (by ~6% five years prior to retirement). Lower activity levels may reduce access to optimal care in times of GP shortage. In this paper, we exploit a natural experiment to verify whether soon-to-retire GPs can be incentivised to maintain high activity rates until the day of retirement.

Background: Danish GPs own their practices and sell their share of the practice upon retirement. The selling price is regulated such that it cannot exceed the GP's “goodwill”, which is set as the average revenue over the last three years plus 30%. This regulation creates an incentive for retiring GPs to increase their revenues to achieve the largest possible goodwill (potential selling price). To test whether the goodwill selling price influences GPs' activity-level we exploit variations in the average selling price across time. In 2001 the average selling price was 113% of goodwill, whereas in 2016 it was only 44%. This variation in the selling price enables us to test whether - and how - the change in the magnitude of the financial incentive alters the retiring GPs' behaviour.

We hypothesize that the size of the financial incentive provided by goodwill determines the potential responses of GPs. When goodwill is high, GPs will increase their activity three years prior to retirement as the financial incentive to do so is strong. However, when GPs' goodwill is low the financial incentive to change behaviour is weaker. Our second hypothesis is that GPs with a previously high activity-level respond less to the financial incentives than those GPs with a previously low activity-level. We base this hypothesis on the assumption that GPs with high activity levels are more likely to be operating at their maximum capacity level and therefore are unable to respond to the financial incentive.

Methods: To estimate the effect of the goodwill on GP behaviour, we compare GPs who are soon-to-retire (3 to 1 years from retirement) with those who are next-in-line to retire (5 to 7 years from retirement). To account for the GPs' previous activity levels, we standardize the outcome variable such that we measure a percentage change in revenues across time. The base year is set to 8 years prior to retirement. We use a linear regression with GP level fixed effects controlling for the complexity of the patient population, list size, and GPs' health.

Data: We use data from the National Health Service Register and the Provider Register, which includes information on Danish practices' activity and characteristics of all GPs (around 3,500 GPs in 2,200 practices) from 1996 to 2014.

Results: We find that when goodwill is high, GPs tend to increase activity. When dividing our sample into high and low activity groups, we find that GPs who previously had a low activity-level respond more to the financial incentive. We conclude that retiring GPs respond to financial incentives, and that such incentives may be a useful tool for ensuring higher activity levels amongst soon-to-retire GPs.